

CONSUMER PREFERENCE AND AWARENESS ON AIRTEL 3G NETWORK

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Abstract:

The project entitled "Consumer Preference and Awareness on Airtel 3G Network" is carried out with the primary objective to find out the consumer preference and awareness towards Airtel 3G network with special reference to Pollachi Taluk. The research method used the convenient sampling method. Samples of 144 respondents were considered for the study. The study has been undertaken for one year [November 2015-April 2016]. The data collected through issuing questionnaire. The data collected is analysed with the tools like Simple percentage, weighted average ranking method. The present study shows that consumer preference and awareness on airtel 3g network.

Key Words: Airtel 3G, Consumer Preference & Consumer Awareness.

Introduction:

3G technology or third generation technology is the convergence of various second generation telecommunication systems. The technology is intended for smart phones or multimedia cell phones. Video broadcasting and other e-commerce services such as stock transactions and e-learning will now made possible, much faster. 3G offers 3MBps speed for downloading, which is very high compared to that of 2G technology. 3G provides for Internet surfing, downloading, e-mail attachment downloading, audio video conferencing, fax services and many other broadband applications. This technology was implemented for the first time in Japan. Today the technology is in operation in 25 countries, with over more than 60 networks in Asia, Europe and USA. The video conferencing capability of 3G has been a major factor in its success. Not only the media and entertainment sector, but the business sector too has started using 3G applications worldwide. Video conferencing allows two individuals across the world to interact in the same way as they could have done, across the table. The technology is being implemented at various functional levels of business, such as marketing, human resources, etc.

Reviews:

Deepti Garg and Ajay K. Garg (2011), indicate high saturation level in terms of usage of mobile phones compared to several countries while the 3G mobile service usage rate was found to be low in comparison to other parts of the world. H. Gruber and P. Koutroumpis (2010), found that the rationale for the differences regarding adoption of 3G services in various countries could be per capita income, urbanization and Internet/Broadband penetration, as well as regulation that positively affect diffusion across all generations of mobile technologies. Sangwon Lee (2009), identifies that multiple standardization policy, lower level of 1G and 2G penetrations, and a higher level of income contribute to the diffusion of 3G mobile.

Statement of Problem:

Essentially, good quality at a cheaper cost and few-value added service and sincere service with smile when you are in trouble are what excellent data service is all about. There are various data service providers in our country and they are playing an essential role fulfilling the needs of the customers. Airtel 3G is one such service provider which has to identify the Indian customer's expectations, based on which they have to provide service. Hence it will be useful for the AIRTEL service provider to know consumers preference for AIRTEL 3G and their awareness towards the Network in Pollachi Taluk. Thus, the following questions arise regarding customer preference and awareness.

- ✓ What is the reason for preferring AIRTEL 3G Network?
- ✓ What is the extent of customer awareness?
- ✓ What are the determinants of customer awareness?

Objectives of the Study:

The following are the objectives of the study:

- ✓ To know the socio-economic profile of sample users.
- ✓ To study on consumer awareness about 3G Airtel Network.
- ✓ To analyze the consumer preference for 3G Airtel Network in Pollachi Taluk.

- ✓ To ascertain the consumer level of awareness.

Research Methodology:

The study is based on primary data which is collected through well framed questionnaire issued to 150 customers of Airtel3G Network in Pollachi Taluk. Of the total 150 questionnaires issued, six found to be incomplete and 144 questionnaires were taken for analysis. Convenient sampling method is adopted to select the sample customers of Airtel3G Network. The data collected have been analyzed using Simple Percentage and Weighted Average Ranking Method.

Limitations of the Study:

- ✓ The study is concerned to Pollachi Taluk.
- ✓ The primary data is collected through questionnaire, so all limitations pertaining to it is bounded.

Findings of the Study:

Socio-Economic Profile of the Respondents – Simple Percentage:

Table 1: Socio-economic Profile of the Respondents

Factors	No. of Respondents (N=144)	Factors	No. of Respondents (N=144)
Area of Residence		Type of family	
Rural	42	Joint	69
Semi-urban	37	Nuclear	75
Urban	65		
Gender		Marital Status	
Male	79	Married	47
Female	65	Unmarried	97
Age		No. of Earning members in the family	
Up to 20 years	25	One	
21 to 30 years	97	Two	47
31 to 55 years	19	Three	56
Above 55 years	3	Above three	36
			5
No. of Non-Earning members in the family		Total No. of members in the family	
One		Two	
Two	37	Three	4
Three	56	Four	31
Above three	44	Above Four	66
	7		43
Educational Qualification		Family Income Per Month	
Illiterate		Up to Rs.20,000	
Up to HSC	10	Rs.20,001 - 30,000	54
Diploma	16	Rs.30,001 - 40,000	47
Under-Graduate	15	Above RS.40,0001	25
Post-Graduate	21		18
	82		
Occupation			
Agriculture	15		
Business	25		
Private Employees	17		
Government Employees	6		
Student	79		
Others	2		

Table 1 shows that, out of 144 customers, 65(45.00%) are customers living in urban area, 79(55.00%) customers are female, 97(67.40%) customer’s age group between 21 to 30 years, 97(67.36%) customers are Unmarried, 82(57.00%) customers are Post-graduates holders, 79(156.00%) customers are Student, 75(52.00%) customers belong to nuclear family, 56(38.89%) customers have two earning members in their family, 56(38.89%) customers have two non- earning members in their family, 66(45.83%) customers have four members in the family, 54(37.50%) customers’ family income per month is Rs. Up to Rs.20,000.

2. Consumers Awareness on Airtel 3G Network – Simple Percentage:

- ✓ Majority (52.30%) of the respondents are level of awareness on private label brand is ‘Aware

- ✓ Majority (36.11%) of the respondents source of awareness about Airtel 3G Network is ‘Advertisement’
- ✓ Period of using Airtel 3G Network is ‘Below Six Months’ by the majority (40%) of respondents
- ✓ Most (70%) of the respondents mode of operating the network is ‘Mobile Phone’
- ✓ Majority (83.33%) of the respondents use ‘Pre-Paid Service’ of the selected network
- ✓ Among the respondents who use pre-paid service, most (56%) of the respondents prefer ‘Monthly Pack’
- ✓ Majority (53%) of the respondents are ‘Highly Aware’ about the 3G Data Scheme feature of the Airtel 3G Network
- ✓ Majority (59%) of the respondents are ‘Aware’ about the Video Calling feature of Airtel 3G Network
- ✓ Majority (48.61%) of the respondents are ‘Aware’ about the Video Conferencing feature of Airtel 3G Network
- ✓ Majority (55%) of the respondents are ‘Highly Aware’ of the High Speed Download feature of Airtel 3G Network
- ✓ Majority (44%) of the respondents are ‘Highly Aware’ about the Social Networking feature of Airtel 3G Network
- ✓ ‘Downloading’ is the main purpose of using Airtel 3G Network by majority of the respondents.

Factors Influencing Customers Preference for Airtel 3G Network:

Table 2: Factors Influencing Customers Preference for Airtel 3G network - Weighted Average Ranking

Factors	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	Total	Rank
Affordability	20	10	5	9	8	14	15	20	43	144	IX
Status	3	16	14	21	8	17	17	32	16	144	VII
Cheaper	9	5	12	19	17	17	28	19	18	144	VIII
Easy Communication	6	16	11	14	21	34	17	16	9	144	VI
High Speed	49	9	9	10	21	7	14	13	12	144	I
Brand Name	13	32	15	13	16	18	16	13	8	144	IV
Attractive Plans and Offers	13	18	25	21	23	9	20	9	6	144	II
Network Connectivity	11	23	27	20	17	13	12	9	12	144	III
Easy Recharge Method	20	15	26	17	13	15	5	13	20	144	V

From the above table, it is observed that among the various reasons, the customers have ranked High Speed as 1st rank for preferring the Airtel 3G network, followed by ‘Attractive Plans and Offers’, ‘Network Connectivity’, ‘Brand Name’, ‘Easy Recharge Method’, ‘Easy Communication’, ‘Status’, ‘Cheaper’ and ‘Affordability’.

Suggestions:

- ✓ The benefits offered by the Airtel service providers should clearly communicated to illiterates through mass media in the form of slogans or informative and descriptive advertisement for improvement of sales.
- ✓ Airtel has to introduce more attractive offers and plans for the customers.
- ✓ The cost for the 3G network can be reduced as it suits for the low income group people also.
- ✓ Airtel should be very clear on their schemes and freebies to dealers and customers.
- ✓ The validity time for the pre-paid cards can be considerably extended.
- ✓ Airtel can make arrangements to improve their network connectivity still more.

Conclusion:

The analysis exposed that there is a considerable percentage of awareness prevailing among the customers about the service of Airtel 3G network. There are some additional factors which affect quality of services. Customer awareness, launch of services by new operators, attractive plans and offers, easy recharge method, high speed etc., The consumers are highly influences by their family members, friends and advertisement while the select on buying Airtel 3G network. The study says that consumers are satisfied with the process of solution of their and queries. The significance development in this field in the past ten years shows that there is a very bright scope for expansion and modernization in Airtel 3G network area with a very short span of time. Consumer preference and awareness is the measuring scale of creditability of the service provided by any organization. Internet service providers are not exceptions to it. This research study gives an opportunity to get the feedback of the customers regarding their preference and awareness level about Airtel 3G network.

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